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Basic Concept of Dravyaguna Vijnana

**Gupta Chandan Kumar¹, Debbarma Salka²,
Kashyap Vinod Kumar³, Jain Yogita⁴, Rudramani Deepak⁵**

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Dravyaguna Vijnana, Shivalik Ayurvedic Medical College Azamgarh, Uttar Pradesh.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Dravyaguna Vijnana, Chandrasekhar Singh Ayurveda Sansthan, Koilaha, Kaushambi, Uttarpradesh

³Assistant Professor, Department of Dravyaguna Vijnana, Shivalik Ayurvedic Medical College Azamgarh, Uttar Pradesh.

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Roga Nidan and Vikriti Vijnana, Shivalik Ayurvedic Medical College Azamgarh, Uttar Pradesh.

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa, Shivalik Ayurvedic Medical College Azamgarh, Uttar Pradesh.

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

Dravyaguna Vijnana deals with the universal principles related to the Ayurveda pharmacognosy and pharmacology. Dravyaguna Vijnana deals with Namajnana, Rupajnana, Gunajnana and Yuktijnana, etc. Literal meaning of word Dravya means material or things and Guna means properties or qualities, thus Dravyaguna Vijnana deals around properties of Dravya (drugs). Dravyaguna Vijnana narrates pharmacological activities with Rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipaka and Prabhava of drugs. As per Ayurveda Rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipaka and Prabhava are integral properties of Ayurveda drugs which pays towards the therapeutic actions of drugs. This article accessible general principles of Dravyaguna and contribution of properties of Dravya near pharmacological actions by which one can understand various Dravya properly

Keywords: Dravaguna, Rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipaka, Prabhava.

1. Introduction

Acharya Priyavrat Sharma defined Dravyaguna Shastra as the branch which deals with the Guna (properties), Karma (action), Prayoga (Therapeutic effect) of various Dravyas (drugs) (1).

Ayurveda in relation to the properties and actions of drugs described in Dravyaguna which involves systematic information on herbs & Ayurveda formulations including their nomenclature, properties & pharmacological actions. Dravyaguna definitely deals with pharmacognosy, pharmacology, therapeutic utility and Samavaya Sambandha (inherent relation) between Guna (properties) and Karma (actions) of Ayurveda drugs.

According to Ayurveda, all Dravya in universe is made up Panchamahabhuta. (2) As per Ayurveda Dravya (drugs) works around concepts of Panchabhuta and Tridosha. Panchabhutas; Akasha, Vayu, Agni, Jala and Prithivi governs physiological activities of body and Dravya (drugs) having specific predominance of Mahabhuta to cure related ailments. (3) Likewise, Tridosha (Vata, Pitta, Kapha) if remain in balance state, then normal physiological functions of body observed, but imbalance of Tridosha leads to pathological actions and specific Ayurvedic drugs works on particular Doshas thus help in specific Dosha vitiation. Properties of Dravya (drugs) modify vitiated state of Doshas by virtue of their Mahabhutas predominance thus exerts their actions on biological system.

As per Ayurveda Rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipaka and Prabhava of drugs govern pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics actions of drugs. Guna described inherent properties of drug, Rasa described taste of drugs, Vipaka means final product after digestion of drugs, Virya denoted to potency of drugs and Prabhava resembles specific potency of drugs. The Dravya (drugs)

responsible for specific Karma(actions).

2. Concept of Guna and its Pharmacological Correlations

Guna means quality or property of drug, the classical texts described various types of Guna of Ayurveda among them Gurvadi Guna (4) which is Chikitsaopyogi Guna (Sharirika Guna) including; Guru, Laghu, Shita, Ushna, Snigdha, Ruksha, Tikshna, Mridu, Kathina, Sukshma, Vishada and Pichhila Guna, etc.

Guru guna quality contributes towards Brihana, (5) the weight gain capacity which helps in emaciated person, these drugs increase Kapha and predominant to Earth and Water elements. Guru Guna pacify Vata Dosa and aggravates Kapha dosa and Chirapaki (heavy to digest) (6). Example Masha, Mushali.

Drug owing Laghu Guna causes lightness in body (7) and such drugs digest quickly and reaches at the site of action easily thus helps to Srotoshodhan (clear minute channels). These drugs regulate circulatory process and control Vata Dosha inside body, predominant of Akash, Vayu and Agni Mahabhuta and pacify Kapha Dosha and aggravates Vata Dosha. These Guna has indication in Varnropaka, Utsahakar. For Ex Mudga, Laja

Dravya which has power of Stambhan called Sheeta (8). Sheeta Guna contributes to soothe Daha (burning sensation) in body, conveys coldness therefore such drug benefits in inflammatory conditions and cures excessive functioning of digestive fire in disease like Amlapitta. Sheeta guna have predominant of Jala Mahabhuta and pacify Pitta Dosha and aggravates Vata and Kapha Dosha. The indication of these Guna in Atisar, Trishna, Dahasamaka, Raktastambhaka . For Ex.- Chandan, Durva etc.

Dravya which has power of Svedan (sudation) known as Ushna Guna (9). Drugs possess Ushna Guna imparts hot potency and increase Ushanata of body thus helps in cold and cough, these drugs increase Pitta and improves digestions thus helps to regulate metabolic actions. These Guna have predominant of Agni Mahabhuta and pacify Vata and Kapha Dosha and aggravates Pitta Dosha. The indication of these Guna helps in indigestion, increase thirst and burning sensation. Ex.- Chitrak, Hingu etc

The Dravyas in which have power of Kledan eliminate dryness of body known as Snigdha (10). These drugs help to pacify excessive dryness of the body. These drugs help in skin disorders and maintain water element of body. The Dravya which has Snigdha Guna helps to keep body soft and moisten and produce strength in the body. These Guna have predominant of Prithvi and Jala Mahabhuta and pacify Vata Dosha and aggravates Kapha Dosha. Ex.- Vasa, Til, Eranda.

The Dravyas which has power of Shoshan called Ruksha (11). Ruksha Guna contributes towards dryness and these drugs helps to counteract excessive oiliness of the body. These Guna have predominant of Vayu Mahabhuta and pacify Kapha Dosha and aggravates Vata Dosha.

3. Concept of Rasa and its Pharmacological Correlations

Artha of Rasana is known as Rasa. (12) Rasa means taste of drugs; Rasa depends upon combination of Bhutas in Dravya. Rasa are six types (13) such as; Madhura, Amla, Lavana, Katu, Tikta and Kashaya. These Rasa offers specific actions on the human body therefore imparts required therapeutic responses.

Madhura Rasa pacifies Pitta and increases Kapha therefore promotes strength and helps exacerbation of Pitta and related disorders.

Dravya having Amla Rasa promote Kapha and Pitta and pacify Vata Dosha thus acts as carminative, appetite stimulant and helps in digestive ailments. Drugs predominate with Amla Rasa imparts Dipana-pachana effects thus boost Agni.

Dravya possesses Lavana Rasa increases Pitta and pacifies Vata Dosha therefore encourage digestive system and helps in anorexia and digestive disorders, since it pacifies Vata thus helps in Vatika disorders.

Ayurveda drugs having Katu Rasa enhances Vata and decreases Kapha therefore control movements of stool and urine. Katu Rasa helps in disorders arises due to the Kapha aggravation. The fiery nature of drugs having Katu Rasa stimulates digestive fire.

Tikta Rasa pacify Kapha and increases Vata Dosha. These drugs acts as penetrable and helps to clear obstruction of minute channels of body. These compounds help in Kaphaja disorders regulates circulatory functioning of body.

Drugs possess Kashaya Rasa control digestive fire, Kashaya Rasa pacifies Pitta Dosha and increases Vata Dosha, drug with Kashaya Rasa helps in Pittaja disorders. These drugs exert Stambhana effects thus helpful in disorder like Diarrhoea and also remedy for bleeding complications.(14)

4. Concept of Vipaka and its Pharmacological Correlations

After ingestion when Ahara Dravya combine with Agni, the Rasa which is produced after digestion is known as Vipak. (15) Vipaka denoted to the final or end product of metabolism i.e., digestion of drugs which produced after digestion process. This biological transformation alter action of drug, means if Katu drug transformed in Madhura vipaka then definitely its action gets altered. Vipaka may be Madhura, Amla and Katu on the basis of taste and on the basis of properties it may be Guru and Laghu.

Drugs having Madhura vipaka increases Kapha Dosha and enable process of excretions. Amla vipaka increases Pitta thus these acts as carminative and improves digestion. Compounds having Katu vipaka increases Vata thus helps to regulates circulatory working of body. Vipaka alter effects of Dosha, Dhatu and Mala thus Vipaka contributes significantly towards the wholesome or unwholesome effect of drugs on body.

5. Concept of Virya and its Pharmacological Correlations

Dravya by which capable to perform its function known as Virya. Dravya unable to perform its karmas in absence of Virya. Hence all the Karmas of Dravya done by Virya. (16) Virya means Shakti or power or potency of drugs, this means strength of drug action towards therapeutic response.

As per Charaka, Virya is that substance by which Dravya (drug) perform its karma (action)(17). Drug action greatly depends upon its Virya, it is specified that if Virya is low then drug not exerts optimal pharmacological actions and vice-versa.

Ex.- Brihat panchamula is Kashya Tikta Ras, so according to principal of Rasa it should be aggravated Vata but due Ushna Virya pacify Vata.

6. Concept of Prabhava and its Pharmacological Correlations

Prabhava is a property which is characterized by specific action of substance which cannot be explained in term of pharmacological action of various constituents of Dravya when they are considered individually in relation to each other (18).

Prabhava is specific influence depends upon particular nature (Bhautika composition) and therefore responsible for specific pharmacological action. Prabhava means nature of specific actions like emesis and purgation, etc. It differs from Virya since Virya referred for general

power while Prabhava resembles definite actions.

It is stated that drugs possessing similar Rasa and Guna but differing in pharmacological action due to their Prabhava. Ex- Danti and Chitrak both have Katu Ras, Katu Vipaka and Ushna Virya, Chitrak possesses Deepan and Pachan Karma but Danti has Virechan Karma (purgation) due to influence of Prabhava.(19)

7. Conclusion

Dravyaguna means properties, action and Yukti Prayog of Dravya and Ayurveda described specific properties of Dravya like; Rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipak and Prabhav. As per Ayurveda Rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipak and Prabhav are integral properties of Ayurveda drugs which works towards therapeutic actions of drugs. Ayurveda concepts supposed that natural drugs apply their actions by virtue of their Rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipak and Prabhav. This concept explains pharmacological significance of taste, properties, active metabolite, potency and specific actions of drug substances.

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